

A Spatiotemporal Clustering Approach to Maritime Domain Awareness

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Abstract—Spatiotemporal clustering is the process of grouping objects based on both their spatial and temporal similarity. This approach is useful when considering the distance between objects and how that distance changes through time. Spatiotemporal clustering analysis is applied to the maritime domain in this paper, specifically to a defined area of water, during a period of time, in order to gain behavioral knowledge of vessel interactions and provide the opportunity to screen such interactions for further investigation. The proposed spatiotemporal clustering algorithm spatially clusters vessels in the water space using k-means clustering analysis, kinematically refines the clusters based on the similarity of vessel headings, speeds and the distance between them, and temporally analyzes the continuity of membership of the kinematic clusters through time to determine which clusters are moving. The algorithm is implemented in the MATLAB programming environment, verified with a synthetic data scenario, and validated with two real-world datasets.

Index Terms—Spatiotemporal clustering, maritime domain

I. INTRODUCTION

Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA) presents a continuous challenge to national strategic decision makers. Defined as “the effective understanding of anything associated with the maritime domain that could impact the security, safety, economy, or environment of a nation,” MDA is based on the concept that maritime security is achieved or improved through developing an understanding of events occurring in the maritime domain [1], [2]. The ability to autonomously classify vessel movement at sea in order to gain behavioral knowledge of a water space is a significant challenge, especially when more than 90% of the world’s commerce is conducted by sea, and non-traditional maritime threats, counter-proliferation, and piracy are increasingly more important to national security.

Previously, much effort has been placed into the development of algorithms that employ time-series analysis to estimate vessel position and predict future vessel location and that determine what normal and, by extension, abnormal behavior of vessels at sea can be considered to be. Specifically, Tunaley describes the development of a ship detection and tracking program that is designed to analyze processed imagery rapidly and inexpensively [3]. Efforts like Tunaley’s support the creation and maintenance of the recognized maritime picture (RMP), but lack analysis of how ships interact and, by extension, a behavioral knowledge of a water space.

The spatiotemporal clustering (STC) concept has been applied in other areas including urban combat environments, georeferenced mobile device tracking, traffic incidents, and the spread of the avian influenza H5N1 in poultry, wild birds, and humans [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], and [9]. In this paper the STC concept is applied to the maritime domain in order to autonomously classify vessel movement at sea in order to gain behavioral knowledge of a water space, specifically to determine when vessels exhibit paralleling or following behavior as an indicator of possible illicit behavior.

Hwang, Kang, and Li [10] propose three methods to perform STC on objects moving on road networks. These methods can be extended to moving vessels at sea:

- Method 1: Form clusters based on spatial clustering and then refine with temporal analysis.
- Method 2: Form clusters based on temporal clustering and then refine with spatial analysis.
- Method 3: Form clusters based on the simultaneous consideration of spatial and temporal analyses.

In this paper the first method is used as the general approach to STC. The second method is not easily translated to the maritime domain because temporal clustering would yield much larger clusters in need of kinematic refinement and, in turn, create a more difficult problem. This would not be an efficient approach to analyzing a water space that has high traffic density, like a major strait. The third method is likely the most robust of the three, but because of the time-latent nature of maritime domain data, it is not necessary to simultaneously consider space and time. The simultaneous accounting of kinematic and temporal attributes creates a larger workload and leads to inefficiencies in the STC algorithms’ performance. Based on the first method above, vessels at sea are spatially clustered and then refined through temporal analysis to form spatiotemporal results that can be processed for further understanding.

To understand the underlying behaviors of paralleling and following, kinematic information is required. Kinematics describes the motion of points in a particular frame of reference, and kinematic similarity between nearby objects can suggest collusion and other behaviors of interest [11]. In this maritime application, vessel characteristics like course and speed will factor largely into determining vessels that are exhibiting paralleling or following behavior. For this reason the

STC algorithm does not exclusively spatially cluster vessels at sea, but rather does so kinematically by considering course and speed characteristics in addition to spatial relationships.

This paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the STC algorithm components of data conditioning, cluster preprocessing, proximity filtering, kinematic filtering, temporal analysis, and the post-processing of spatiotemporal results to create easily understood text and visual outputs. Section III details the set-up and results of the simulation scenario and real-world data analyses. Conclusions are presented in Section IV.

II. SPATIOTEMPORAL CLUSTERING ALGORITHM

The method of forming clusters kinematically and performing temporal analysis to form spatiotemporal clusters is applied to the maritime domain. An overview of the proposed algorithm is presented, followed by an in-depth explanation of the progression and development of the STC algorithm, with a focus on its six stages: 1) data conditioning, 2) cluster preprocessing, 3) proximity filtering, 4) kinematic filtering, 5) temporal refinement, and 6) post-processing of spatiotemporal results.

The algorithm begins with an input dataset consisting of vessel position reports during a specific timeframe. After user-provided input for parameter definitions, the data is submitted to a data conditioning stage in which time indices are assigned and the data is formatted, filtered, and converted. The proximity filtering stage spatially refines the position attributes of the vessel position reports, and through kinematic filtering, clusters of vessels are formed at each time-step based on similarity of vessel courses, speeds, and distance between them. The kinematic clusters are temporally refined to determine which of them can be considered moving clusters and which are only present at one instance in time. Once vessel position reports have been analyzed both kinematically and temporally, the results are spatiotemporal in nature and completely describe how the kinematic relationships between vessels change over time. Behavioral knowledge of the water space can then be gained through post-processing of the results and interpretation of the text and visual outputs. The progression of the six stages of the STC algorithm along with data input and behavioral knowledge output are depicted in Figure 1.

A. Input

As illustrated in Figure 1, there are two types of input provided to the STC algorithm. The first is the collection of vessel position reports, which is the bulk data the STC algorithm analyzes to gain behavioral knowledge of the water space of interest. The second input is the user-provided input. Different parameters must be defined, either through use of default values or through manual input, to enable the various stages of the STC algorithm to function.

Figure 1. Top-level view of the spatiotemporal clustering algorithm.

B. Data Conditioning

Data conditioning is the stage in which the input dataset is formatted and aligned for STC algorithm use. First, time indexing, the process of converting UTC seconds to a time-step assignment, an integer greater than or equal to one, is applied to the input dataset. UTC seconds are converted to the time and date of the timestamp, and then, with the user input for start hour, start minute, and time window length, the time and date is converted to a time-step value t . A function designed to ensure that each MMSI or vessel identifier has only one position report for each time-step is also applied. If a vessel has more than one report in a time-step, the vessel attributes from the multiple reports are averaged to form one representative report for the time-step.

Second, the dataset is formatted and placed in the correct order so that the required data fields are properly aligned for STC algorithm use. Each unique AIS vessel attribute report is stored as a row in the matrix Ψ in which each column represents a vector of different attribute from the AIS data as

$$\Psi = \begin{bmatrix} x & y & r & s & m & t \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where Ψ is of size $L_{AIS} \times 6$, and L_{AIS} is the number of AIS vessel reports in the input dataset. The variables are all vectors of length $L_{AIS} \times 1$ and x and y describe each vessel's position on the x - y coordinate grid, r its course, s its speed, m its MMSI, and t its time-step assignment.

C. Cluster Preprocessing

Cluster preprocessing is the introduction of vessel identity indexing and the decomposition of Ψ into manageable pieces for STC algorithm analysis. During the clustering preprocessing stage, each unique MMSI in the vector m is assigned an index q beginning at 1 and continuing until each unique MMSI has an assignment. The index q will be used as a subscript to identify which vessel's attributes are being used.

The Ψ matrix is decomposed by time-step assignment into a three-dimensional matrix ψ of dimension $L_t \times 4 \times N_t$, where N_t represents the maximum number of time steps, L_t is

the number of vessels in each time-step, and $\sum L_t = L_{AIS}$. The data matrix ψ^t can be represented at the t -th time-step as

$$\psi^t = \begin{bmatrix} x^t & y^t & r^t & s^t \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where

$$x^t = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ x_q \end{bmatrix}, y^t = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ y_q \end{bmatrix}, r^t = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ r_2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ r_q \end{bmatrix}, \text{ and } s^t = \begin{bmatrix} s_1 \\ s_2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ s_q \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

and q is the vessel identity index.

D. Proximity Filtering

Proximity filtering, accomplished through the use of k-means clustering, identifies spatial relationships between vessels at a particular time-step. Only x and y position data of ψ^t is considered. The optimum number of centroids k available for assignment is calculated from the length of ψ^t at the time-step being analyzed as [25]

$$L_t = 2k \log(k). \quad (4)$$

To determine the specific centroids at each time-step, the farthest-first methodology is used [25]. The x and y position information for the contact in the first row of ψ^t is designated as the initial centroid. The second through k -th centroids are chosen to be the contact that has the maximum Euclidean distance from the previously selected centroid. For example, for $t=1$ the first contact of ψ^1 is designated as the first centroid. The second centroid is chosen as the contact that has the greatest distance from the first centroid, where distance is calculated as

$$d = \sqrt{(x_n - x_1)^2 + (y_n - y_1)^2} \text{ for } n = 2, 3, \dots, L_t. \quad (5)$$

The third centroid is chosen as the point that has the greatest distance d from the second centroid and so on.

Then the centroids are used to perform k-means clustering on the position data in ψ^t to spatially refine the contacts by assigning each contact to one of the centroids. The contacts associated with each centroid j at each time-step t are stored in a matrix c_j^t of size $L_{t_j} \times 4$ where L_{t_j} is the number of contacts assigned to each centroid at each time-step as

$$c_j^t = \begin{bmatrix} x^t & y^t & r^t & s^t \end{bmatrix} \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, k, \quad (6)$$

where x^t , y^t , r^t , and s^t are vectors of size $L_{t_j} \times 1$ containing the respective attributes for the vessels in the cluster. After all contacts have been assigned to a centroid, k-means cluster assignments for a time-step are stored in a cell array ξ^t as

$$\xi^t = \left\{ c_j^t \quad c_{j+1}^t \quad \cdot \quad \cdot \quad \cdot \quad c_k^t \right\}. \quad (7)$$

A cell array is a set of matrices of different dimensions. At the completion of the proximity filtering stage there is a cell array ξ^t for each time-step that contains the k-means assignment for all contacts in that time-step.

E. Kinematic Filtering

Kinematic filtering is used to further refine the clustering results from the proximity filter to form clusters of contacts with attributes that exhibit paralleling or following behavior as defined by the user. In kinematic filtering, the similarities of course and speed attributes of vessels, as well as the distance between them, are determined for each k-means cluster. In each cluster c_j^t in ξ^t , a seed contact σ is determined as the vessel with the maximum speed in c_j^t to initialize kinematic filtering as

$$\sigma = \max(s^t), \quad (8)$$

where s^t is a vector of speeds in c_j^t . To formulate kinematic clusters, three thresholds are defined. The heading difference between the seed contact and all other contacts in c_j^t is defined as

$$T_H = |r_{q_\sigma} - r_{q_p}| \text{ for } p = 2, 3, \dots, L_{t_j}, \quad (9)$$

the speed difference is defined as

$$T_S = |s_{q_\sigma} - s_{q_p}|, \quad (10)$$

and the distance between them is defined as

$$T_D = \sqrt{(x_{q_\sigma} - x_{q_p})^2 + (y_{q_\sigma} - y_{q_p})^2}. \quad (11)$$

If T_H , T_S , and T_D are less than the user defined thresholds for maximum heading difference, maximum speed difference, and maximum distance between contacts, the contacts associated with q_σ and q_p are classified as a kinematic cluster ϕ_l^t and are represented as

$$\phi_l^t = \left\{ \begin{matrix} q_\sigma \\ q_p \end{matrix} \right\} \text{ for } l = 1, 2, \dots, L_{t_j} \quad (12)$$

where i is the number of kinematic clusters for each time-step of ξ^t . The length of ϕ_l^t varies and is dependent on the number of contacts that when compared with the seed contact result in T_H , T_S , and T_D values that are less than the user defined thresholds. The contacts assigned to ϕ_l^t from c_j^t are removed from further consideration for assignment to another kinematic cluster.

A new seed contact is determined so that T_H , T_S , and T_D may be calculated for the remaining contacts in c_j^t to discover other kinematic clusters as described in Equations (8)-(12). The

iterative process continues until all contacts in c_j^i have been considered for assignment to a kinematic cluster. Upon completion, a snapshot of the kinematic clusters in ξ^i are compiled in a cell array β^i for temporal analysis as

$$\beta^i = \left\{ \phi_1^i \quad \phi_{i+1}^i \quad \dots \quad \phi_{L_i}^i \right\}. \quad (13)$$

An example of a k-means, distance, and velocity kinematic clustering result is illustrated in Figure 2 in which there are four kinematic clusters identified at time-step two of a generic simulation. The maximum distance between contacts was defined as four nautical miles for the simulation, and each of the four resultant clusters are displayed in a different color. The contacts of each cluster were initially grouped by proximity filtering and further refined kinematically by determining similarities between vessel headings, speeds, and the distance between them.

Figure 2. An example of k-means, distance, and velocity kinematic clustering results at time-step two of a generic simulation.

F. Temporal Refinement

Temporal refinement determines which kinematic clusters are moving in time and which are not. The input data to this stage are cell arrays that contain the membership of the kinematic clusters for each time-step. To determine which kinematic clusters are moving in time, it is necessary to calculate the similarity of the membership of the kinematic clusters in consecutive time steps. The first kinematic cluster in β^i , ϕ_1^i , is designated as the reference cluster, and the intersection of ϕ_1^i and each kinematic cluster in β^{i+1} is calculated as

$$I = \text{length}(\phi_1^i \cap \phi_v^{i+1}) \text{ for } v = 1, 2, \dots, L_{\beta^{i+1}}. \quad (14)$$

If an intersection is found between ϕ_1^i and a cluster in β^{i+1} , the variable fuse f is calculated as

$$f = \frac{I}{\text{length}(\phi_1^i)}, \quad (15)$$

and the next cluster in β^i , ϕ_{i+1}^i , becomes the reference cluster.

If an intersection is not found between ϕ_1^i and a cluster in β^{i+1} , the intersection is calculated between ϕ_1^i and each kinematic cluster in β^{i+2} as in Equation (14). If an intersection is found, fuse is calculated as in Equation (15). If an intersection is not found, ϕ_1^i is removed from consideration as a moving cluster and the second cluster in β^i , ϕ_{i+1}^i becomes the reference cluster, and the process is repeated.

Once all kinematic clusters in β^i have served as the reference cluster for intersection calculations, the kinematic clusters of β^{i+1} beginning with ϕ_1^{i+1} become the reference clusters. This iterative process continues until all the clusters in $\beta^{\max(i)-1}$ have served as the reference cluster. Kinematic clusters in $\beta^{\max(i)}$ are not considered in temporal refinement due to the lack of future kinematic clusters with which to calculate intersections.

When a value other than zero is calculated for f , it is compared to the user-defined moving cluster threshold value. If f is greater than or equal to that value, the associated kinematic cluster ϕ_1^i is stored to the cell array δ as

$$\delta = \{\phi_1^i\}, \quad (16)$$

where δ is of size $1 \times L_{MC}$ and L_{MC} is the number of moving clusters determined in temporal refinement.

G. Post-processing of Spatiotemporal Results

Upon completion of temporal analysis, three cell arrays, each containing spatiotemporal results, are constructed. Through post-processing of these cell arrays, it is possible to build usable outputs to determine information about the selected water space, including the detection of moving clusters of vessels that are exhibiting paralleling or following behavior and the ability to track vessel interactions over time.

1) Identifying Members of a Moving Cluster

The first cell array δ represents all kinematic clusters that move through time for a minimum of two time steps with a minimum threshold of continuous membership in the variable fuse f as

$$\delta = \left\{ \begin{array}{cccc} \phi_1^i & \phi_{i+1}^i & \phi_{L_i}^i & \cdot \\ \phi_{i+1}^i & \phi_{i+2}^i & \phi_{i+3}^i & \phi_{L_i}^i \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \phi_1^z & \phi_{i+1}^z & \phi_{i+4}^z & \cdot \end{array} \right\} \quad (17)$$

where z is the maximum time-step that contains a moving cluster. The row location of any cluster ϕ in the cell array σ indicates the time steps at which the moving cluster exists. For

example ϕ'_{i+2} that appears in the second row, is a moving cluster that begins at time-step two.

Further analysis of this cell array provides details such as when a moving cluster forms, which contacts are members of the subject moving cluster, if contacts join or leave the cluster, and when, if ever, the cluster's membership becomes low enough that it can no longer be considered a moving cluster.

2) Kinematic Clusters Occurring at the Last Time-step of Data

The cell array ρ is equal to β' at the last time-step of available data and is of size $1 \times L_i$, where L_i is the number of kinematic clusters found in β' . Due to a lack of future time steps with which to compare this time-step of data, these current clusters are stored as a matter of interest to the user as

$$\rho = \left\{ \begin{array}{cccc} \phi_i^{\max(i)} & \phi_{i+1}^{\max(i)} & \cdot & \cdot & \phi_{L_i}^{\max(i)} \end{array} \right\}. \quad (18)$$

The clusters in ρ are not known to be moving clusters but represent only the kinematic clusters of the last time-step of data. Information detailed in ρ is displayed only in the text output, under the "Moving Clusters" section, to avoid unnecessary cluttering of the visual output.

3) Generation of the Contacts of Interest List

The third cell array, θ , is the same size as δ , but rather than containing cluster membership information, it contains the global identity index q of contacts that either join or leave clusters. Vessels that move together as a moving cluster for several time steps are of interest to an analyst, but a vessel that joins a cluster then departs it, and then joins another cluster, is also of interest. The information contained in θ is displayed only in the text output, under the "Contacts of Interest" section.

4) Post-processing of Spatiotemporal Results to Form Usable Outputs

The post-processing of the spatiotemporal results stored in the cell arrays δ , ρ , and θ is the transfer of data into usable outputs for better user understanding. Post-processing of the cell arrays results in the generation of two outputs. One output is text based and the other is a visual representation of moving vessel clusters in the water space.

a) Text Output

The text output has two distinct parts, *Moving Clusters* and *Contacts of Interest*. The *Moving Clusters* part provides the global identifiers of the members of each moving cluster, as well as the time at which the cluster is formed and the time at which the cluster ceases to exist. Current clusters are also detailed in this manner in the text output. The second part of the text output, *Contacts of Interest*, results from the ρ cell array and contains the global identifier of any contact that joins or leaves an existent moving cluster, as well as the time at

which the event occurs. If the contact is deemed to be leaving a moving cluster, the text output also details the heading and speed of the contact's departure. If there are two or more contacts that depart a larger moving cluster and continue to move as a smaller moving cluster, then the heading and speed reported is an average of the two contacts. An example of both parts of the text output is presented in Figure 3 where there are fourteen moving clusters identified and three contacts of interest defined.

b) Visual Output

The visual based output is an interactive, MATLAB-generated plot that depicts the position and track of each moving cluster analyzed by the STC algorithm. In Figure 4, there are several moving clusters displayed, some red, some orange, and some green, each color indicating the membership of the moving clusters as defined in Table 1. The position, heading, and speed of each moving cluster displayed is computed by averaging its constituent members' respective attributes. For example, for a given moving cluster, the speed reported is the average speed of all vessels contained within that specific cluster. Moving clusters are marked by an 'x' for each time-step that they occur and with an 'o' at their final time-step of occurrence. If a moving cluster is only present for two time steps, it is represented by an 'o'. The markers and track lines on the plot are color-coded to detail the degree of membership that the moving cluster maintains.

Moving Clusters:

Cluster 1 containing contacts 12 13 14 15 16 17 begins at time 1 and ends at time 1
Cluster 2 containing contacts 18 19 20 21 22 begins at time 1 and ends at time 1
Cluster 3 containing contacts 12 13 14 17 begins at time 2, is a current cluster, but gains or loses members
Cluster 4 containing contacts 25 30 begins at time 2 and ends at time 9
Cluster 9 containing contacts 18 19 begins at time 11, is a current cluster, but gains or loses members

Figure 3. An example text output from the STC algorithm's analysis of a generic simulation scenario.

The MATLAB plot also has an interactive functionality, which is illustrated in Figure 4. The user is able to click on any marker of a moving cluster to determine which cluster is represented, at which time-step the cluster occurs, as well as the cluster's position, heading, and speed. In Figure 4 it is determined that moving cluster 4 exists at time-step two, in position $(-8.67, -1.33)$ heading 157° at 23 knots. To discover which contacts compose moving cluster 4, it is necessary to reference the first portion of the text output. Upon doing so, it can be determined that the contacts in moving cluster 4 have vessel identifiers of 25 and 30.

Figure 4. An example visual representation output of the STC algorithm’s analysis of a generic simulation scenario.

Table 1. The MATLAB interactive plot color-code key for moving cluster membership identification.

Display Color	Percentage Membership Indicated
Red	100%
Orange	75% - 99%
Green	50% - 74%
Blue	25% - 49%
Violet	0% - 24%

In this section, the six stages of the STC algorithm were detailed. Vessel data and user-provided input were discussed as the primary inputs to the STC algorithm. The data conditioning and cluster preprocessing stages, where datasets are time indexed, formatted, and aligned for algorithm use, were discussed. Proximity and kinematic filtering were defined and the attributes each considers were given. Temporal refinement to determine which clusters move through time was detailed, and examples of the usable outputs formed from post-processing of spatiotemporal results were presented.

III. RESULTS

The STC algorithm is implemented in the MATLAB programming environment. To verify operability and validate its possible use, the STC algorithm is tested using synthetic and real-world datasets. The thresholds used for the simulation and real-world analyses are defined in Table 2.

A. Verification Using Synthetic Data

The synthetic data simulation is run using data that was purposefully created in order to test the functionality of the STC algorithm. Specifically, the synthetic scenario provides proof of concept that the algorithm can properly evaluate the user-selected values from Table 2, and that the text and visual outputs are operable. The synthetic data simulation involves a

dataset of three hundred vessel position reports taken over a period of seventy-two minutes, or six time-steps.

In the simulation, two separate scenarios are executed. Scenario one consists of two contacts and is designed to test maximum heading difference between contacts and maximum distance between contacts. Scenario two begins with two groups of five contacts each, and is designed to test maximum speed difference between the contacts, maximum distance between contacts, and the operability of the moving cluster threshold value. The data is provided to the STC algorithm for processing. A portion of the text and entire visual output are presented in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Table 2. Threshold values for simulations

Parameter	Value for Synthetic and AIS Real-World Scenarios	Value for GPS Real-World Scenario
Time Window Length	12 Minutes	1 Minute
Maximum Heading Difference Between Contacts	39°	10°
Maximum Distance Between Contacts	8 Nautical Miles	0.5 Nautical Miles
Maximum Speed Difference Between Contacts	16 Knots	5 Knots
Moving Cluster Threshold Value	60%	25%

From the text output we expect there to be five moving clusters in the visual representation. Upon inspection of Figure 6, there are five moving clusters, four marked in red, indicating that they maintain 100% membership during their existence, and the fifth marked as a cyan circle, indicating it only exists for one time-step. The moving cluster at the top-left of Figure 6 consists of two contacts that were designed to test the maximum course heading difference and maximum distance between contacts thresholds. During the three time-steps in which the two contacts are within the defined thresholds, they are kinematically clustered and tracked as a moving cluster, as illustrated in Figure 6. The two outer red moving clusters at the bottom of the visual output are meant to test the maximum speed difference between contacts and the maximum distance between contacts. The kinematic clusters begin as two separate moving clusters during the first two time-steps. For the following three time-steps, the two clusters fall within the thresholds for distance and speed difference and are classified as one large kinematic cluster, represented visually by the center red cluster. In the fifth time-step the large moving cluster’s membership reduces by 40% in order to test the storage threshold value. The moving cluster is expected to continue to be tracked, and is marked by the cyan circle. In the

sixth time-step of the simulation, none of the synthetic contacts meet kinematic clustering requirements, and are not tracked.

Moving Clusters:

- Cluster 1 containing contacts 10 11 12 13 14 begins at time 1 and ends at time 2.
- Cluster 2 containing contacts 15 16 17 18 19 begins at time 1 and ends at time 2.
- Cluster 3 containing contacts 1 2 begins at time 2 and ends at time 4.
- Cluster 4 containing contacts 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 begins at time 3 and ends at time 4.
- Cluster 5 containing contacts 10 11 12 17 18 19 begins at time 5 and ends at time 5.

Figure 5. A portion of the synthetic simulation text output.

Figure 6. Synthetic simulation visual output.

B. Validation Using Real-World Data

After successfully evaluating the synthetic data scenarios, the STC algorithm was tested on two real-world datasets. For the first analysis, the real-world data source is worldwide Automatic Identification System (AIS) vessel position reports for the twenty-four hour period beginning at 0001, 10 January 2012. The International Maritime Organization requires AIS to be fitted aboard international voyaging ships with gross tonnage of greater than 300 tons, and all passenger ships regardless of size [14]. The water space of interest for the analysis was chosen to be the Strait of Malacca. The Strait of Malacca, which is the main shipping channel between the Indian Ocean and the Pacific Ocean, is considered one of the most important shipping lanes in the world, with more than 60,000 vessels passing through it each year [15].

The purpose of the real-world data analysis is to illustrate the STC algorithm’s ability to process a robust and relatively large set of data. On 10 January 2012 there were slightly more than 1.5 million worldwide AIS vessel position reports,

approximately five thousand of which occurred in and around the Strait of Malacca.

1) AIS Real-world Data Concerning the Strait of Malacca

To set-up the scenario we present a hypothetical report that the Motor Vessel (M/V) Mairini with Maritime Mobile Service Identity (MMSI) number 538003897 was involved in an illicit cargo transfer on 10 January 2012. It is our desire to determine which vessels M/V Mairini interacts or travels with for any period of time on 10 January. The worldwide AIS data is provided to the STC algorithm, and the outputs are presented in Figure 7 and Figure 8.

Moving Clusters:

- Cluster 1 containing contacts 477093700 477583000 477759800 begins at time 19 and ends at time 19
- Cluster 2 containing contacts 533001330 533281000 begins at time 20 and ends at time 20
- Cluster 3 containing contacts 353525000 355461000 begins at time 87 and ends at time 88
- Cluster 9 containing contacts 538002853 538003897 begins at time 98, is a current cluster, but gains or loses members

Figure 7. The STC algorithm text output for the AIS real-world data analysis of the Strait of Malacca on 10 January 2012.

Figure 8. STC algorithm visual output for a AIS real-world data analysis of the Strait of Malacca on 10 January 2012. Moving cluster 9 containing two contacts travels on average heading 126 at an average speed of 13 knots.

2) AIS Real-world Data Results

Through examination of the text output, it is clear that the vessel of interest did indeed interact with another vessel on the day in question. By converting the time-steps to time of day, we can determine that M/V Mairini interacted with another vessel around the time of 1936 Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) on 10 January 2012. Per the text output, the two vessels are a moving cluster at the latest time-step that contains kinematic clusters, time-step 116, which is equivalent to 2312 GMT. We

must be careful not to interpret this report to mean that the two vessels moved together for the entire timespan from 1936 until 2312, but rather that they are clustered together at multiple time-steps during those four hours.

The underlay of the Google map on the visual output provides situational awareness to the user. The MATLAB interactive capability that was highlighted in the synthetic simulation is also present here, and also provides further insight as to the situation. The moving cluster in question, cluster 12, has been selected in Figure 8, and its attributes are displayed. The cluster was moving on an average course of 126° at a speed of 13 knots at time-step 98, and when the two vessels are last clustered at time-step 116, they are moving on an average course of 114° at a speed of 14 knots. From the visual representation in Figure 8, it appears that the moving cluster is on a standard transit course through the Strait of Malacca. While the results of the real-world data analysis are not conclusive evidence that M/V Mairini was involved in hypothetical illicit behavior, they do offer enough insight as to the vessel's interactions on the day in question for an analyst's further scrutiny.

3) GNSS Real-world Data Concerning Vehicles Imitating Small Boats

The second real-world data analysis is performed on GPS data gathered over a twenty-three minute period from 1514 to 1537 UTC on 24 April 2013 via GNSS transmitters mounted on six vehicles driving on Route 3 in Massachusetts. The vehicles operate in a manner to simulate small boats traveling together. The drive-plan for the vehicles dictated three of them to form a convoy and maintain speed and distance for the span of the exercise. The other three vehicles acted as confuser vehicles and moved in and out of the convoy. One of the convoy vehicles was unable to report heading data and was, therefore, excluded from STC algorithm analysis. The analysis from the STC algorithm reveals that multiple moving clusters are tracked over the twenty-three minute period, which is in keeping with the drive-plan, which is summarized in Table 3.

4) GNSS Real-world Data Results

According to the drive-plan, vehicles 3, 4, and 6 form the convoy and should regularly be clustered as a moving cluster over the span of the twenty-three minute dataset. Vehicle 3 did not transmit heading data, so the STC algorithm did not analyze it. The remaining vehicles should move in and out of the convoy and form various moving clusters during the run. From the visual representation in Figure 9 and the text output in Figure 10, it is evident that several moving clusters are tracked in the analysis of the dataset. Vehicles 4 and 6, which form the convoy, are not explicitly clustered together for the length of the analysis but are detailed in the "Contacts of Interest" section as a moving cluster that joins and departs other clusters. This designation provides evidence that contacts 4 and 6 move together for much of the twenty-three minute run as directed in the drive-plan. With user thresholds set as

previously detailed, thirteen moving clusters are identified during the analysis. The confuser vehicles moving in and out of the convoy account for a majority of these cluster changes. In Figure 9 moving cluster 9 consisting of vehicles 1, 2, and 6 is identified.

Table 3. GNSS real-world data analysis vehicle drive-plan.

Vehicle	Drive Plan
1	Confuser: drive alongside/lead/trail/enter/exit convoy, pass other confusers
2	Confuser: drive alongside/lead/trail/enter/exit convoy
3	Convoy lead: drive at/near speed limit in right lane
4	Convoy middle: do not change convoy order, vary follow spacing, allow confusers to enter/exit convoy
5	Confuser: drive alongside/lead/trail/enter/exit convoy
6	Convoy tail: do not change convoy order, vary follow spacing, allow confusers to enter/exit convoy

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The work presented in this paper provides three contributions to the MDA problem set. First an STC scheme was developed and applied to the maritime domain to identify interactions between vessels at sea in order to gain behavioral knowledge of paralleling and following movement in a water space. The scheme was validated using multiple data sources that provided a real-world hypothetical scenario in the Strait of Malacca and a simulated movement of small boats

Figure 9. STC algorithm visual output for a GNSS real-world data analysis of vehicles imitating small boats on 24 April 2013.

Moving Clusters:

Cluster 1 containing contacts 5 6 begins at time 5 and ends at time 24
Cluster 2 containing contacts 1 2 begins at time 5, is a current cluster, but gains or loses members
Cluster 9 containing contacts 1 2 6 begins at time 12 and ends at time 15
Cluster 12 containing contacts 4 6 begins at time 22 and ends at time 22
Cluster 13 containing contacts 1 4 begins at time 24 and ends at time 24

Figure 10. STC algorithm text output for GNSS real-world data analysis of vehicles imitating small boats on 24 April 2013.

Second, three filters were designed in support of the operation of the STC algorithm. Location filtering enabled a large input dataset to be focused onto a specific water space of interest. The proximity filter spatially refined the input dataset by grouping contacts via k-means clustering centroid assignment. Kinematic filtering then determined the similarity of vessel course and speed within each k-means cluster and further spatially refined the clustering process by comparing the distance between vessels.

Finally, the STC algorithm provided those interested in national or theater security decision making the opportunity to quantify the (membership) continuity of a moving cluster. A group of vessels deemed to be exhibiting paralleling or following behavior by the algorithm were tracked until the continuity fell below the user-defined threshold of interest. The opportunity to quantify the continuity allows the user to characterize the degree to which a moving cluster may change.

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